

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Perceived Influence of Human Capital Development on Teachers in the Public Secondary Schools in Ohaukwu L.G.A of Ebonyi State.

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Abstract: The purpose of the study was to examine the human capital development of secondary school teachers in Ohaukwu local government of Ebonyi State. Two research questions and one hypothesis were used to guide the study. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The sample size of 234 teachers was used for the study representing 30% of the entire population. The tools used for the data analysis in the study were percentages and t-test. The findings among others revealed that human capital development of teachers has a positive influence on their teaching effectiveness, such as effective classroom management, managing time-table, conceptualize subject matters, disciple of students, present teaching logically and communicate effectively. It was recommended that the government should organize workshops comprising all the headteachers, assistants and teachers so that all of them can benefit. The workshop should not select few.

Keywords: Public Schools, Human Capital Development, Teachers.

INTRODUCTION

It is widely acknowledged that human capital development can help a nation to overcome many of the characteristics of the labour force that act as impediments to greater productivity such as illiteracy, lack of incentive, no receptiveness to new knowledge, poor health, fear of change and immobility. Human capital development helps the labor force to be more efficient and the realization of Modern industrial-technological requirements.

Secondary education is the education that children receive in a school system after primary education before the tertiary level. Its broad goal includes the preparation of the child for useful living within the society. According to Adeyemi (2009), secondary education is to provide all primary school leavers with the opportunity for higher education. It inspires students with teaching towards self-improvement.

Teaching is a skill that requires the gathering of relevant information to the students following the prescribed methodologies (Arabayi, 2013). He further stated that human capital development is vital for all categories of teachers. According to kulwant (2011), regular training and development of teachers and other incentives should be introduced for proper academic growth, higher productivity, and teaching effectiveness, so that they could serve the society in the best possible way. Training and development of secondary school teachers help to acquire knowledge, skills, and development of positive behaviour and attitude to work as an effective teacher.

Human capital development of secondary school teachers enables them to have additional

indicators of quality teaching to drive students learning. Therefore, the need arose to carry out an empirical study on the need to enhance the human capital development of secondary school teachers for effective teaching.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Nigeria been rocked by labor unrests prompted by nonpayment of salaries, among other factors (Dike, 2010), some problems militating against the quality of the teacher in the Nigerian education and they include; poor health care services for teachers, poor educational qualifications, poor water supply and provision of toilet facilities for teachers, poor access and transaction to school, lack of payment of salary. Thus, teachers have a poor quality of life and this could however significantly impede teachers and even educational efficiency and development.

This is because all these will make teachers inefficient and no or little energy might be devoted to both teaching preparation and teaching activities. Against this backdrop, it becomes exigent to carry out an empirical study on enhancing human capital development of secondary school teachers for effective teaching.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The major purpose of this study was to examine the human capital development of secondary school teachers in Ohaukwu local government area of Ebonyi state and their teaching effectiveness. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the role of government in enhancing human capital development of secondary school teachers in Ohaokwu L.G.A of Ebonyi state
2. Determine if human capital development of secondary school teachers influences their teaching effectiveness

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following two research question guided the study;

1. What is the role of the government in enhancing the human capital development of secondary school teachers in Ebonyi State?
2. What are the possible influence of human capital development of secondary school teachers and their effectiveness in Ohaokwu L. G .A of Ebonyi State?

NULL HYPOTHESIS

The null hypothesis that guided the study was 0.05 significance. Ho: there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the influence of human capital development of secondary school teachers and their teaching effectiveness.

METHODS

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. A descriptive survey describes the nature of the existing conditions (Maduakonam, 2004). The population of the study was drawn from all the teachers in the public secondary schools in Ohaukwu L.G.A of Ebonyi State. There are thirty secondary schools with a population of 780 teachers in the Ohaukwu Local Government Area.

The sample size of the study was 234 teachers representing 30 of the entire secondary

school teachers in the local government areas using the ballot method. A 22 items self –made questionnaire was used to elicit information from the respondents. A four-point likert scale format of strongly agree, agree, disagree, strongly disagree was and numerical values of 4,3,2,1 were assigned to each of the four points respectively. A total of 234 questionnaires were distributed and collected by the researcher. Data collected were analyzed using simple percentages.

Result question 1: what is the role of government in enhancing human capital development of secondary school?

Table 1: sample percentage of governments role in enhancing human capital development of primary school teachers.

S/ No	Items	No. Agreed	%	No. Disagreed	%	Decision Rule
1	Government organizes regular training such as conferences and workshops for secondary school teachers.	220	94%	17	65%	Accepted
2	All the secondary school teachers participate in the training programs.	80	34%	154	66%	Rejected
3	Government approves in-service training (Sandwich weekend programs) for secondary school teachers.	110	47%	124	66%	Rejected
4	The training enrolment is always conducive	60	26%	7174	53%	Rejected
5	Participant are properly fed during training	50	21%	184	74%	Rejected
6	Participants are given a transport allowance	50	21%	184	79%	Rejected
7	The resource persons (facilitators) are qualified and competence	60	24%	210	79%	Rejected
8	Resource materials (reference materials, bags, biro, jotters, pencil)etc	180	79%	54	24%	Accepted

Source: Agbii; Chukwu & Iwundu Field Survey 2019.

The above table 1 showed that the government organizes regular training (94%). The resource persons were qualified and competence (89%) resource materials were provided (76%). The table also revealed that items 2,3,4,5 and 6 were rejected. These findings are contrary to kulwant (2000) who stated that human capital development is vital for all categories of teachers but government organizes workshops regularly for few selected teachers not for the teachers to benefit fully but for their selfish interest.

The responses of secondary school teachers to research question two revealed that human capital development does not influence the recommendation of the texts for public

secondary schools. The finding buttressed the fact that the state government recommends textbooks for public secondary schools to maintain the academic standard in the State. It was also revealed that secondary school teachers did not acquire any skills of computer training that were not included in their training program.

It was accepted that human capital development of teachers has a positive influence on their teaching effectiveness such as effective classroom management, managing time-table, conceptualize subject matter, the discipline of a student, present teaching logically and communicate effectively, responds to students' questions and problems and participate in staff meetings.

Research question 2: what is the possible influence of human capital development of secondary school teachers on their teaching effectiveness?

Table 2: simple percentage of the influence of human capital development of secondary school teachers on their teaching effectiveness

S/No	Items	No. Agreed	%	No. Disagreed	%	Decision Rule
	Training of secondary school teachers assist them to:					
1	Have effective classroom management	200	84%	24	16%	Accepted
2	Manage time table effectively	150	64%	84	36%	Accepted
3	Use time table during lessons for relevant task	220	94%	14	6%	Accepted
4	Avoid hurry in the lesson	150	64%	84	36%	Accepted
5	Conceptualized the time table	224	96%	10	4%	Accepted
6	Give stimulating information and materials	120	51%	114	49%	Accepted
7	Discipline students	215	92%	9	8%	Accepted
8	Present teaching logically and communicate effectively	150	64%	84	36%	Accepted
9	Stimulate and motivate students to learn	140	60%	94	40%	Accepted
10	Respond to students question/ problems	120	51%	114	49%	Accepted
11	Give feedback to students performance	130	56%	194	44%	Accepted
12	Participating and staff meetings and making wise decisions	180	77%	54	23%	Accepted
13	Recommend textbooks for students	84	36% ¹	150	64%	Rejected
14	Acquire computer skills	10	4%	224	96%	Rejected

Source: Agbii; Chukwu & Iwundu Field Survey 2019.

Table 2: revealed that virtually all the items raised were accepted items except items 13 and 14 i.e. recommendation of textbooks (36%) and acquiring computer skills (4%) were rejected. This means that the human capital development of secondary school teachers has a positive influence on their teaching effectiveness.

Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female teacher son the influence of human capital development of secondary. School teachers and their teaching effectiveness

Table 3:

T-test summary for a significant difference between male and female teachers on the influence of human capital development of teachers

Variables	N	x	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male teachers	102	3.31	1.39	232	1.34	1.96	Ho is not rejected
Female teachers	132	3.36	1.43				

The result from table 3 revealed that the calculated t-value (1.34) is less than the critical t-value(1.96) and so, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This means that both male and female teachers have a uniform opinion on the influence of human capital development of secondary school teachers and their teaching effectiveness.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The responses of secondary school teachers to research question one (table one) showed that Ebonyi State government organizes workshops periodically for only a few selected teachers. The resource person(facilitators) were qualified and competence. Resource materials were given to participants the workshops organized were for the principals, assistance and the few selected teachers. In-service training such as a sandwich, weekend programs, study leave with or without pay, a scholarship was seldom approved for primary school teachers.

The training environment was not conducive for participants because no adequate chairs and tables, the hall not well ventilated. The participant was not properly fed and the transported allowance was not-given to then at the end of the workshop based on distance. These findings are in line with Mari and Peretomode (2001) stressed that training, retraining, and development of secondary school teachers help them to increase their knowledge, skills and development of positive behavior and attitude to work which invariably improves their teaching effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

We should appreciate the fact that the role of secondary school teachers is to educate the students and the society. Teachers are the foundation of quality in any education, therefore, they are the center of the educative process. Consequently, it is on the quality of secondary school teachers acquired through human capital development their efficiency, resourcefulness, and productivity can influence their teaching effectiveness

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. The government should organize workshops comprising all the senior masters, assistants and teachers so that all of them can benefit. The workshop should not be selected a few.
2. The workshop environment should be conducive thus it should be well ventilated, good light system and adequate chairs and tables should be provided for participants (teachers)
3. The participants should be properly fed because anybody hungry cannot Participant meaningfully at the workshop.
4. Teaching computer skills to participants (teachers) is very essential for teachers. The knowledge acquired can assist them in the computation of results, keeping records and other information in the school system. Therefore Ebonyi State Government should introduce computer training skills as the human capital Development of secondary school teachers.
5. Ebonyi State Government should Endeavour to provide at least a set of computer with internet facilities to all the secondary school teachers in the state and the teachers should be made to have access to the computer periodically

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